

Characteristics of personal sound and noise exposure at large-scale music events

Wannes Van Ransbeeck^{a*} Nele De Poortere^{a†} Marcel Kok^{b‡} Sarah Verhulst^{a§}

^a Ghent University, Department of Information technology, Hearing Technology@Waves, Belgium

^b dBcontrol, the Netherlands

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Abstract

Regulations governing sound exposure at amplified-music events aim to safeguard audience’s hearing. However, current sound monitoring practices often rely on a single measurement position that is considered representative of individual exposure. Because this standard practice overlooks crucial inter-subject variation in sound exposure, this study analyzes individual dosimeter sound level exposure at large-scale music events to gain insight into this matter while comparing findings to local and global guidelines. Dosimeters were worn by 42 participants (19f, 23m, aged 18-25) and recorded octave bands and A/C-weighted sound levels at six large-scale music events (+4.000 visitors). Individual single-day exposure duration varied between 4.4 and 11.8 hours. At four out of the six events, individual doses surpassed the WHO 100 dBA $L_{Aeq,15min}$ recommendation, with most subjects also exceeding the ISO1999 occupational limit and the WHO’s 100 dBA-for-4-hours threshold (16 Pa²h). Equivalent exposures spanned [85.2,104.5] dBA (L_{Aeq}) and [97.1,119.6] dBC (L_{Ceq}) among participants. Additionally, L_{Cpeak} values fluctuated between [133.6,143.5] dBC. These findings highlight a discrepancy between the fixed-location exposure monitoring, as per country-specific legislation, and the actual potentially harming exposure experienced by event attendees. Our results can inspire safe-listening guidelines for such music events and offer insight into the representative degree of a single-position measure.

1 INTRODUCTION

At large-scale music events or festivals, the sound levels attendees are exposed to depend on multiple factors, such as the whereabouts of the attendee at the venue [1], venue characteristics (tents, open-air, indoors), meteorological conditions, local topography, crowd numbers, and lastly, the music type (e.g. rock, techno or classical) [2].

Concerts and music events are significant sources of non-occupational high-intensity music [3] and due to their high emitted sound levels, amplified music events pose the most serious threat to hearing health among non-occupational exposure sources [4]. Attendance to these events can thus cause (permanent or temporal) hearing impairment, as exposure to excessive sound levels is known to damage the auditory system [5, 6]. This exposure can cause temporal or permanent hearing threshold shifts and even lasting effects, such as tinnitus, hyperacusis, dullness, etc. [3, 7, 8, 9, 10]. Strikingly, the broad worldwide popularity of amplified music events poses an elevated risk to hearing damage for a significant portion of adults [11] and especially for the younger population (1.1 billion as estimated in 2015 by the WHO) [12]. A careful monitoring and control of emitted

*email: wannes.vanransbeeck@ugent.be

†email: nele.depoortere@ugent.be

‡email: info@dbcontrol.nl

§email: sarah.verhulst@ugent.be

sound levels is thus essential along with promoting the use of hearing protection among attendees [7, 13, 14, 15, 16].

To avoid potentially harmful sound exposures, multiple countries impose guidelines and regulations at music events to control exposure (Table 1). Globally, the World Health Organization (WHO) recommends safe listening guidelines. Worldwide, noise and sound guidelines or standards originate from both occupational exposure regulations [1] as ISO 1999 [17] and the European Directive (2003/10/EC – noise) [18]. To prevent noise-induced hearing damage, the ISO1999 guideline limits exposure by setting a daily exposure threshold of 85 dBA over an 8-hour period to prevent noise-induced hearing damage. This guidelines can then be extended to other durations by applying the Equal Energy Hypothesis (EEH). A 3dBA increase in level to 88 dBA would then still be considered safe for a 4-hour exposure as having the same energy as the original 8 hours at 85 dBA. Furthermore, this energy can be considered through its dose value. In it, the sound pressure (Pascal) is multiplied with the duration of the exposure and expressed in Pa²h to reflect the same accumulated exposure.

Alternatively to ISO1999, the WHO safe-listening limit specifies an elevated upper limit at 100 dBA ($L_{Aeq,15min}$) and further restricts these exposures to a maximum of 4 events lasting each 4 hours per year.

For amplified music events in particular, the present regulations often define an upper limit on the level as recorded at one location, the Front of House (FOH). At these locations, often near the event’s mixing unit, local regulations enforce a threshold on the sound pressure level (SPL; NEN-EN-ISO 9612:2009). The frequency spectrum can then be weighted, allowing emphasis or reduction of specific spectral bands. For instance, A-weighting (L_A) predominantly considers spectral energy between 1 and 6 kHz to reflect a reduced human sound perception below 250Hz (ISO 226:2003). Other weightings can include different spectral ranges, such as C-weighting (L_C) which also includes the bass content of the music. Additionally, the time frame of the sound pressure level measurement provides a clear distinction between instantaneous measurements, which focus on sound peaks during exposure (L_{Cpeak}), and time-averaged values covering either the entire exposure duration (L_{Aeq} , L_{Ceq}) or specific segments ($L_{Aeq,15min}$, $L_{Aeq,1min}$). A descriptive overview of regulations within Europe is present in Table 1 with a more in-depth discussion in work by Beach et. al [19].

Regardless of the power of regulations in preventing hearing damage, their effectiveness is limited by the quality and locality of the measurement. For control of regulation, often a single calibrated microphone is placed at the front of house near the mixing desk [19]. We note that adaptations to this limited locality do exist where a correction for the central audience area is made as suggested in the WHO guidelines [20]. Nevertheless, often the audience can be situated between the monitoring microphone and the sound system. Personal exposure may then be louder and depend on the listener’s location within the venue [9]. Individual exposure variation is thus omitted and more precise measurement protocols may be required which incorporate audience exposure, as suggested by Mulder et. al [21]. Areas with sound levels above the FOH could be considered in guidelines as previously adopted by the WHO and Switzerland [19, 20], either through separate monitoring or limited access. Expanded monitoring standards could then improve safe listening, although the potential overestimation of individual exposure as well as subject variability may hinder their application feasibility. Consequently, an optimization problem emerges aimed at finding an enjoyable sound level for the entire audience while safeguarding listening levels [22]. Favorable implementations of this trade-off seem to be possible and have been achieved before [2].

In all, a clear insight into the individual experienced levels cannot be directly derived from regulatory measurement. Crucial information on individual exposure levels during music events is thus lacking, which is necessary to assess the impact of these exposures on hearing [1].

2 BACKGROUND

Despite its clear relevance, studies on the individual sound exposure at amplified music events are scarce [1] along with in-depth understanding of how regulations relate to them. Initial insights resulted from work by Opperman et. al and Yassi et. al [5, 6] who mapped out individual levels (L_{Aeq}) for different audience locations and concerts. At each concert, mean L_{Aeq} was around 100 dBA with peaks above 100 dBA and daily doses exceeding the daily work limit of ISO1999. However, while both papers monitored individual variation, the seated nature of the audience results in limited representability of more complex event exposures with freedom to roam. Other work by Hill et. al [23] presents the same limitations.

Another study collected subject-specific sound exposures over a 6-day Swiss music festival [2], with L_{Aeq} averages of 95 +- 3.1 dBA ranging between [87.3,103.8] dBA and sound exposure lasting

between 4 and 12 hours per day. Here only a limited fraction of attendees (8%) was exposed to sound levels above 100 dBA. These results reflect in-place local regulations for the event, stating an upper limit of 100 dBA L_{Aeq} over the entire exposure area. Similarly, individual sound levels at a Norwegian study at two music festivals [1] ranged between [87.3,99.4] dBA and [85.5,95.9] dBA. The mean average daily dose corresponded to a 4-h equivalent level across subjects of 97.5 dBA (8.9 Pa²h). Remarkably, despite regulations being enforced only at one festival ($L_{Aeq,30min} < 99$ dBA), both Norwegian events complied with the WHO 4-hour limit of 100 dBA L_{Aeq} (16 Pa²h). Limited individual exceedances above the local regulations did occur at the two events, along with large variations in the personal dose up to 47 Pa²h. With regulations being enforced in the majority of these studies (Switzerland, Norway, Minneapolis, Canada) they provide an initial view on the individual levels at regulation monitored events. Still, the common roam freedom at festivals and large-scale events is only considered within the Norwegian and Swiss study.

This paper aims to further bridge this gap between FOH exposure data and the individual dosimetry. Specifically, the study evaluates individual and global exposure characteristics and relates these to the present regulations and guidelines imposed in the countries where measurements took place, i.e. Belgium (BE) [24] and the Netherlands (NL) [25]. The relation between the presented exposure measurements and links to (temporary) hearing damage is presented elsewhere [26]. The analysis initially focuses on sound level variation among participants in dynamic range and equivalent exposure levels. Subsequently, the analysis broadens to encompass both inter-participants and inter-event variation with in-depth consideration of low frequency content. Moreover, the analysis highlights individual differences in exposure duration, accumulated dose, and overall exceedance of guidelines from Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany and the World Health Organization. This paper concludes by underlining insights stemming from the observed individual exposure and their dynamic ranges.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Exposure dosimetry data of 42 participants (19f, 23m, aged 18-25) was recorded on 6 large-scale amplified music events (F1,F2,F3,F4,F5,F6) in Belgium or the Netherlands during the spring and summer of 2022 (exposures lasted between 4 and 24 hours), see Table 2. From this initial sample, 3 subjects were excluded due to malfunctioning equipment. An initial limited analysis, prior to subject removal, of the recorded individual exposures levels can be found in [27].

Before the event, the hearing thresholds of each attendee were determined by tympanometry and conventional audiometry. Hence, bias due to impairment or hearing loss on exposure behavior was limited as clinical normal hearing was verified for each subject. In-depth information regarding hearing screening, pre- and post-event results and recruiting are further detailed in De Poortere et. al [26]. Similarly, the majority of data collection was performed by De Poortere. Note that the levels as presented here only reflect individual exposure levels and do not indicate guidelines or law compliance of any of the events. Compliance with local regulation was ensured by careful and close monitoring at the FOH.

As a baseline, this paper uses $L_{Aeq,15min}$ regulations to assess the relation between exposure and imposed guidelines. These regulations include limits from the WHO, Belgium, and the Netherlands (100 dBA, 102 dBA, and 103 dBA respectively), along with German peak exposure regulation ($L_{Cpeak} < 135$ dBC) and WHO’s non-occupational dose guidelines [28] ($L_{Aeq} = 100$ dBA for 4 hours). Combined, these guidelines reflect a detailed representation of exposure, including instantaneous exposure and accumulated exposures over the entire duration.

The participants’ individual noise exposure was captured by Casella dBadge2 noise dosimeters [32] equipped with a 1/2” diameter microphone covered with a foam windscreen. The dosimeters were clipped onto either participant’s clothing or bags on shoulder height to properly capture ear exposure. Sound exposure recordings consisted of both L_{Aeq} and L_{Ceq} (ISO 9612) at two different time resolutions: spanning the entire exposure duration and finer 1-second intervals. Additionally, C-weighted peak sound levels (L_{Cpeak}) allowed more effective capture of short peak events. For these peak levels, exceedance of the German guideline was registered per 10ms intervals as well.

To evaluate guidelines, A-weighted sound levels for the 15-minutes and 1-minute intervals were derived from the 1-second intervals with appropriate time weighting using equation 1 (ISO 9612).

$$L_{p,Aeq,T} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\frac{1}{T} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} p_A^2(t) dt}{p_0^2} \quad (1)$$

Equation 1 calculates the A-weighted equivalent sound pressure over a given interval T (in seconds). It uses the individual A-weighted pressure p_A , measured in Pascals at each time instance t within

Table 1: Guidelines and regulations for sound and noise exposure at events.

Country	
Belgium	$L_{Aeq,15min} = 102$ dBA [24] $L_{Aeq,60min} = 100$ dBA
The Netherlands	$L_{Aeq,15min} = 103$ dBA [25] $L_{Cpeak} = 140$ dBC
Germany	$L_{Aeq,30min} = 99$ dBA [29] $L_{Cpeak} = 135$ dBC
France	$L_{Aeq,15min} = 102$ dBA[30] $L_{Ceq,15min} = 118$ dBC
Norway	$L_{Aeq,30min} = 99$ dBA [31] $L_{Cpeak} = 130$ dBC
WHO	$L_{Aeq,15min} = 100$ dBA [20]
WHO dose	$L_{Aeq} = 100$ dBA (4 h at 4 events)[28]
ISO 1999 dose	$L_{Aeq} = 85$ dBA (8 h)[17]

Table 2: Properties of individual events.

Event	Genre	# Visitors	Duration (h)
F1	Dance	15.000	11
F2	Dance	4.000	11
F3	Rock	80.000	13
F4	Techno	20.000	11
F5	Hardcore / Dance	10.000	13
F6	Dance	70.000	13

the window of interest defined by t_1 and t_2 . The reference pressure p_0 , is set at $20\mu\text{Pa}$. Additionally, equation 2 (ISO1999) calculates the total received exposure $E_{A,T}$ for comparison against the ISO1999 and the WHO limit on total received exposure. In this context, accumulated exposure over time will be referred to as “dose” for clarity.

$$E_{A,T} = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} p_A^2(t) dt \quad (2)$$

In equation 2 , p_A represents the individual A-weighted pressure in Pascal at each time instance t between t_1 and t_2 , given in hours. The resulting dose unit is expressed within this paper in Pa^2h (Pascal squared hours). The dynamic range of an individual’s exposure is calculated as the difference between the highest and lowest presented sound level in $L_{Aeq,15min}$.

Recordings covered the entire event, activated from the participant’s arrival till their departure, excluding initial mounting and unmounting of the dosimeter. Exposures lasted between 4.4 hours and 24 hours, with four participants attending a two-day event. To standardize and mitigate skewing from the two-day measurements, only single-day exposures of the first day were considered. All values and analyses hence reflect single day exposure at the measured events. The latter extends to exceedances, dose measurements and peak values as well.

Additionally, ear protection and worn time by each participant were recorded for future reference, however, they are not considered within this paper. The recorded sound exposure thus reflects the worst-case unattenuated sound to the participant. The latter assumption is justified by the often limited worn ear protection by festival attendees [5]. Hence, the attendees surrounding the recorded participant will more likely still perceive the levels as unattenuated and are considered

as such. Additionally, a separate behaviour could be expected between attendees with and without hearing protection to achieve the same experience, as the former perceive the levels as more attenuated. However, no notable differences in sound exposure emerged between those who used protection and those who did not (unpaired sample t-test, $P > 0.01$). Thus, an overestimation of participant exposure is absent given the similar observed behavior regardless of worn hearing protection.

Table 3: Equivalent exposure levels (A and C-weighted) of original recording and corrected version for bag cover at event F3.

Subject	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
<hr/>						
L_{Aeq} (dBA)						
Original	85.5	93.3	85.5	93.7	94.0	93.3
Corrected	85.7	93.4	85.7	93.9	94.4	93.4
Change	0.24	0.15	0.24	0.16	0.35	0.17
L_{Zeq} (dBZ)						
Original	98.0	101.4	98.0	102.3	102.6	101.8
Corrected	98.1	101.4	98.1	102.3	102.6	101.8
Change	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.02

During the measurements, regular checkups were carried out at each event to verify the active recording and correct mounting. However, at event F3 (6 participants) heavy rainfall prompted the use of loosely mounted plastic bags around the microphone foam for protection. Potential spectral alterations for these recording were hence evaluated. Based on DPA microphones' measurements [33] and limited thickness of the bags (0.03 mm) a potential 5 dB attenuation was estimated in the highest frequency bands of the dosimeters (4 kHz, 8 kHz). Recalculation of the L_{Aeq} and L_{Zeq} for these subjects, while considering high-frequency attenuation, resulted in a maximum underestimation of exposure of 0.35 dBA and 0.04 dB respectively, Table 3. Considering peaks in exposure as similar in spectral content to the full measurements content, the majority of energy is observed to be situated below 1 kHz. Hence, the impact of the plastic bags (4 kHz, 8 kHz) on L_{Cpeak} levels is assumed minimal. The covers are expected to mainly affect A-weighted sound levels (L_{Aeq}), which contain the overall lowest sound levels for these subjects, likely also due to the rainfall. Consequently, there might be an overestimation of the lower limit in the observed A-weighted range across all attendees, which will be taken into account.

Furthermore, the partial closure of musical venues during rainfall significantly influenced participant's behavior, leading to extended periods away from the musical performance and reducing measured sound levels. Besides the rainfall, L_{Cpeak} values are potentially underestimated since peak measurements saturated at 143 dBC on the dosimeters and thus limited the capture of higher peak levels.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Individual Exposure Variability

Figure 1 illustrates the 15-minute equivalent sound pressure exposure distributions ($L_{Aeq,15min}$) of four subjects as recorded during the various events, showcased in 5 dBA bins.

The equivalent exposures L_{Aeq} reveal individual disparity in $L_{Aeq,15min}$ distribution for similar L_{Aeq} . Panel b and c display this variation in these values and overall distribution of sound levels for similar L_{Aeq} . The observed dynamic range among individuals in $L_{Aeq,15min}$ spans [24.8,42.6] dBA in Figure 1, and [12.6, 42.6] dBA across all subjects. Participants exposure in $L_{Aeq,15min}$ values across events spanned [68.0,115.0] dBA, where nearly all attendees (excluding three from F3) exceeded the 15-minute 100 dBA WHO guideline at least once per event.

4.2 Across subject exposure

Regarding the exceedances of guidelines hereafter, it should be stated that they by no means reflect non-compliance with local FOH guidelines and regulations. A clear distinction exists between the enforced legislation imposed by authorities throughout the events and the individual personal levels, which are not governed by specific laws or guidelines at these events. The measurements thus reflect only personal behavior.

Figure 1: Individual exposure profiles in A-weighted equivalent sound pressure level per 15-minute $L_{Aeq,15min}$ (dBA re. 20 μ Pa) intervals, accumulated in 5 dBA bins. Black bars reflect exceedance of WHO limit at 100 dBA with percentages indicating 15-minute intervals below the guideline (in grey). Equivalent exposures is given by dashed lines and exposure duration between brackets

In view of this, Figure 2 provides an overview of the pooled behavior in 15-minute intervals for all participants (a) and the distribution of L_{Aeq} over the entire exposure duration (b) using 1 dBA bins. The distribution of $L_{Aeq,15min}$ ranges between [68.0, 115.0] dBA and between [85.3, 104.5] dBA for L_{Aeq} . As a side note, the highest recorded values of $L_{Aeq,15min}$ (114.3, 114.7 and 115.0 dBA) should be handled with care as they appear to be caused by 1-minute peak levels exceeding 120 dBA, and are considered to be more likely a consequence of a faulty reading caused by movement or wind.

During FOH regulated periods, 36% of individual $L_{Aeq,15min}$ exposure intervals exceeded the WHO guideline of 100 dBA across events. Extension of this guideline to equivalent exposure (Figure 2, Table 4), indicates 56.0% of the attendees experienced an L_{Aeq} surpassing 100 dBA. The skewed distributions also suggests a non-normal, general extreme value distribution (GEV), shown in Figure 2, along with GEV distribution parameters for both L_{Aeq} and $L_{Aeq,15min}$.

Figure 2: Sound exposure distributions across participants in 15-minute intervals (a, 1dBA bins) and sound exposure distribution of individual full-duration equivalent exposure (b, 1dBA binsize). Black areas indicate values exceeding the 100 dBA $L_{Aeq,15min}$ WHO guideline. GEV parameters: (a, shape:0.38 loc:93.41 scale:8.26) & (b, shape:0.70 loc:98.96 scale:3.99)

Table 4: Summary of $L_{Aeq,15min}$ exposure intervals and instances surpassing WHO (100 dBA), Belgian (BE,102 dBA) and Dutch (NL,103 dBA) guidelines at guideline-compliant events.

Event	# 15min intervals	> WHO	> BE	> NL	L10 (dBA)	L50 (dBA)	L90 (dBA)
All	1408	509(36%)	333(24%)	249(18%)	104.5	97.2	85.3
1	323	158(49%)	121(37%)	96(30%)	105.9	99.8	88.2
2	196	63(32%)	26(13%)	9(5%)	102.4	95.0	86.2
3	141	1(1%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	97.3	88.7	77.7
4	173	89(51%)	61(35%)	37(21%)	103.7	100.1	92.9
5	256	94(37%)	62(24%)	52(20%)	104.8	96.9	84.4
6	319	104(33%)	63(20%)	55(17%)	104.8	95.3	85.1

Table 5: Global sound pressure level L_{Aeq} percentiles across 39 recorded participants

#	>WHO	L10 (dBA)	L50 (dBA)	L90 (dBA)
39	22(56%)	103	100.3	93.6

Global and per event, exposures and exceedances are given in Table 4 by the percentile sound levels (L10, L50, L90 dBA) indicating the levels at which 10, 50 or 90% of the total recorded duration were spent respectively. The majority of time, around 64% (in 15-minute intervals), was spent below 100 dBA with a median sound level of 97.2 dBA. With the exception of F3, some time period exceeded the guidelines for $L_{Aeq,15min}$ at each event, while complying with local regulations. Minimum exceedance percentages of total time per event amounted to 32%, 13%, and 5% for the WHO, Belgian, and Dutch guideline respectively. Table 5 details percentile information in L_{Aeq} across events, with mean and standard deviation per event listed in Table 6. Table 6 additionally lists the standard deviation and mean of both the $L_{Zeq,62Hz}$ and the $L_{Zeq,125Hz}$ per and across events.

For the accumulated exposure, Figure 3 presents the dosage distribution across subjects per day, in bins of 16 Pa²h, with doses surpassing the WHO guideline (16 Pa²h, black line) marked in darker tones. The average individual dosage was 43.1 Pa²h, and individual values ranged from [1.1,120.3] Pa²h, including event F3. Notably, a total of 18% (7 out of 39) of attendees received a daily dose at the events below the WHO guideline with five of the subjects attending F3. For attendees exceeding the guideline, hearing protection was worn by 47% of the participants while being a slightly lower percentage for those below the threshold at 43%.

Equivalent individual exposures with A and C-weighting are illustrated in Figure 4(a) per event together with the WHO guideline for $L_{Aeq,15min}$ (black line). Additionally, panel (b) displays the corresponding low frequency exposure. Across events, there was a consistent 8.3dB, or higher, difference between L_{Aeq} and L_{Ceq} means per event with attendee L_{Aeq} levels ranging from [85.3,104.5] dBA, slightly surpassing the 100 dBA reference by maximally 4.5 dBA, while adhering to the FOH guideline. Excluding F3, due to rainfall and limited exposure, per event mean L_{Aeq} values ranged between [98.2,102.1] dBA. The per event mean L_{Ceq} , including F3, ranged from [109.6,116.7] dBC, while $L_{Zeq,62Hz}$ ranged in [108.9,116.8] dB and $L_{Zeq,125Hz}$ between [100.0, 106.7] dB.

Table 6: Equivalent exposure mean and standard deviation per event and across events.

Event	L_{Aeq}		L_{Ceq}		$L_{Zeq,62Hz}$		$L_{Zeq,125Hz}$	
	M (dBA)	SD (dBA)	M (dBC)	SD (dBC)	M (dB)	SD (dB)	M (dB)	SD (dB)
All	99.5	3.8	112.6	5.6	111.7	6.4	102.3	4.5
1	102.1	1.2	116.3	0.9	115.7	1.1	106.7	2.0
2	98.2	1.2	109.6	0.7	108.9	0.7	100.0	0.7
3	91.8	3.3	100.3	1.7	97.2	1.4	93.6	1.4
4	101.8	1.6	113.5	0.5	112.3	0.6	105.0	1.7
5	100.8	2.8	116.7	3.8	116.8	3.8	101.7	3.6
6	100.2	1.0	116.3	1.4	115.7	1.5	104	1.3

Using a two-tailed Mann-Whitney U test, each individual event was compared for significant ($P < 0.001$) differences (L_{Aeq} and L_{Ceq}) compared to the collection of all other events combined.

Figure 3: Distribution of doses across events and subjects, in 16 Pa²h bins. The vertical line indicates the WHO guideline of 16 Pa²h (100 dBA for 4 hours). People wearing hearing protection (HP) and those without (NHP) are separated by hashing. Doses exceeding the guideline are marked in a darker color, i.e. to the right of the WHO guideline.

Figure 4: A and C-weighted distribution of the individual equivalent sound pressure levels per event (a) and low frequency content evaluated at 62Hz and 125Hz (b).

As 50% of events had a P-significance around 0.01, a 0.001 threshold seemed adequate to best capture strong differences from group statistics. Hence, only event F3 differed significantly from the grouped other events in L_{Aeq} (Mdn: 92.5 dBA vs. Mdn: 100.8 dBA, $U = 0$, $n_1=5$, $n_2=34$, $P<0.001$). Similarly for L_{Ceq} , event F1 (Mdn: 116.3 dBC), F2 (Mdn: 109.6 dBC), and F3 (Mdn: 100.3 dBC) significantly deviated from their respective remaining groups (Mdn: 113.1 dBC, $U = 23$, $n_1=7$, $n_2=32$, $P<0.001$), (Mdn: 114.1 dBC, $U = 35$, $n_1=7$, $n_2=32$, $P<0.001$), and (Mdn: 114.1

dB, $U = 0$, $n_1=5$, $n_2=34$, $P<0.001$). These differences suggest potential influences of rainfall (F3) and possible differences in musical content or system setup for (F1,F2,F3).

4.3 Comparison between personal exposures and FOH regulations & guidelines

Figure 5 illustrates the individual exceedances of German peak regulations ($L_{Cpeak} < 135$ dB) and $L_{Aeq,15min}$ guidelines (Belgian (102 dBA), Dutch (103 dBA), WHO (100 dBA)), relative to the individual equivalent exposure levels L_{Aeq} . Note that these exceedances do not indicate non-compliance of the events with guidelines and local regulations. Furthermore, microphone clipping affected the recording for some participants, resulting in a skewed range of C-weighted peak values (L_{Cpeak}) between [133.6, 143.5] dBC. Hence, L_{Cpeak} values are excluded from the analysis and German guideline exceedance counts (135 dBC) per 10 ms interval are only considered and given in Figure 5. The regression lines in Figure 5 indicate a relationship between individual

Figure 5: Individual exceedance of the German L_{Cpeak} (a, 135dBC) and $L_{Aeq,15min}$ guidelines of the WHO (b, 100 dBA), Belgium (b, 102 dBA) and the Netherlands (b,103 dBA), relative to the individual equivalent exposure L_{Aeq} . Linear regressions and Pearson correlation (r) are illustrated with significance marked by asterisks ($*P<0.01$, $**P<0.001$). Brackets denote inclusion of event F3.

exceedance counts (L_{Cpeak} , $L_{Aeq,15min}$) and equivalent individual level L_{Aeq} . They signify a present interdependence and additional value of both for a detailed representation of the individual exposure.

Instances of L_{Cpeak} (135 dBC) exceedances across subjects varied between [0,75e3], with 98.7% of attendees (88.2% excluding F3) experiencing at least one peak level above the German guideline. A moderately significant correlation ($r = 0.37$ $P = 0.022$, $r = 0.42$ $P = 0.013$ excluding F3) occurs between L_{Cpeak} exceedance and L_{Aeq} . Alternatively, $L_{Aeq,15min}$ exceedance correlation to L_{Aeq} were significant ($P<0.001$) for the WHO, Belgian, and Dutch guidelines with respective Pearson correlation [0.67, 0.66, 0.66] and [0.78, 0.71, 0.67] including F3. Most participants (88.1%, 83.3% and 81.0%), including F3, exceeded the respective 100 dBA, 102 dBA, and 103 dBA guideline, with FOH guidelines and regulations maintained.

4.4 Durations and exposure behavior

Table 7: Mean and standard deviation of exposure duration per event.

Event	All	1	2	3	4	5	6
M (h)	9.13	11.66	7.05	7.21	6.33	10.75	11.47
SD (h)	2.36	0.06	0.05	0.88	1.15	0.49	0.36

Figure 6: Summed one-minute equivalent exposures ($L_{Aeq,1min}$) averaged across participants per event in 5 dBA bins (a) and across participants distribution of summed exposures boxplots in hours (b).

Figure 6 represents the individual exposure distribution using one-minute $L_{Aeq,1min}$ in 5 dBA bins. Exposure duration peaked mostly around 100 dBA (± 2.5 dBA) with individual subject peaks varying between 85 dBA and 105 dBA. Subjects displayed a skewed distribution in exposure levels, typically with a right shifted peak and associated faster drop-off to the right. The four highest median times were spent in the bins of 90 dBA, 95 dBA, 100 dBA, and 105 dBA each lasting [1.45, 1.58, 2.20, 1.35] hours, respectively. Table 7 provides the exposure duration and its deviation among subjects per event. Daily individual exposure duration varied between [4.4, 11.8] hours, averaging at 9.1 hours with 2.36 hours of standard deviation. This effects event-specific variation in behavioural patterns in terms of exposure duration.

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Individual exposure variability

Individual sound exposures varied significantly in levels, as observed in both $L_{Aeq,15min}$ levels [68.0,115.0] dBA and their dynamic ranges (Figure 1). These variations, resulting from diverse factors such as user behavior, meteorological conditions, music genre, and other factors, challenge the effectiveness of equivalent exposure as singular representation of exposure (Figure 1, panels c and d). While L_{Aeq} values can appear similar (99.7 dBA, 100.1 dBA), they inadequately represent the wider dynamic range of $L_{Aeq,15min}$ (25.9 dBA and 42.6 dBA) of both attendees. Comparison by equivalent levels L_{Aeq} as isolated measurements thus overlooks detailed variations in shorter time frames, potentially misjudging two exposures as equivalent and thus impacting guideline exceedance assessment. Figure 1 demonstrates this discrepancy, with panels a and d illustrating more frequent guideline exceedances of $L_{Aeq,15min}$ for elevated equivalent sound levels L_{Aeq} (4% in panel a, and 52% in panel d). Contrarily, panels b and c show increased exceedance for a slightly lower L_{Aeq} (panel b 99.7 dBA and panel c 100.1 dBA). Hence, a reduced equivalent sound level does not warrant fewer exceedances.

The equivalent sound pressure levels L_{Aeq} portray only a partial view of the individual variation, potentially masking harmful occurrences by averaging low and high sound intensities and has similarly also been reported by sound engineers as limiting real-time feedback of the exposure [34]. A lack of a fine-grained representation of the exposure might thus skew exposure perception, reflected by most subjects (35 out of 39) surpassing the 100 dBA $L_{Aeq,15min}$ WHO guideline at least once, despite a proper guideline-controlled level at the Front of House similar to prior research [35].

5.2 Across subject exposure

The equivalent exposure L_{Aeq} across attendees further underlines the present subject-specific spread. Exposure averaged to 99.3 ± 3.8 dBA ranging between 85.2 and 104.5 dBA. This vari-

ance and mean were notably higher compared to similar studies at Norwegian festivals [1], which reported L_{Aeq} values of 93.4 ± 1.0 dBA (range: 87.3 to 99.4 dBA) and 92.6 ± 0.7 dBA (range: 85.5 to 95.9 dBA), as well as a 6-day Swiss festival [2] with $L_{Aeq} = 95.1 \pm 3.1$ dBA (range: 87.3 to 103.8 dBA). Nevertheless, levels reaching 100 dBA have been reported at rock concerts and other music events [19,20], and are expected in the individual levels based solely on the local guidelines and the individual’s positioning relative to the stage.

Across all subjects and events, 90% of the individual 15-minute intervals were above 85.3 dBA, 50% above 97.2 dBA, and 10% above 104.5 dB. These figures correspond closely to Front of House measurements reported at other events [1] (L90 = 88.3dBA, L50 = 96.7 dBA, L10 = 103.8 dBA, 1-minute intervals). Nevertheless for individual exposure, Tronstad et. al [1] found deviating individual sound levels (L90 = 60.5 dBA, L50 = 81.8 dBA, L10 = 97.5 dBA, 1-minute), with less variation and lower overall sound levels compared to the exposures observed here. Furthermore, attendees spent 36% of their time above the $L_{Aeq,15min}$ WHO guideline of 100 dBA (Figure 2), which is also significantly higher than previous studies (5.7%) [1]. Similarly, the portion of subjects exceeding 100 dBA (56%) for equivalent sound pressure levels surpasses earlier event work by Mercier et. al [2], which reported only 8% exceedance among subjects. Concerning the Belgian (102 dBA) and the Dutch (103 dBA) guidelines, 24%, and 18% of all $L_{Aeq,15min}$ personal dosimetry measurements surpassed the respective limits, despite the present regulations and control monitoring at the Front of House. A loss in representation of variability within the L_{Aeq} measurement is also reflected by a decreased standard deviation of equivalent exposures (L_{Aeq}) at 3.8 dBA to the 15-minute $L_{Aeq,15min}$ representation (7.8 dBA).

The mean accumulated exposure stood at 43.1 Pa²h across participants, notably surpassing the WHO recommended limit [28] of 4 hours at $L_{Aeq,4h} = 100$ dBA (16 Pa²h) with a significant portion of subjects (82%) at doses above this guideline. However, as exposures lasted up to 12 hours (Table 7) and equivalent sound pressure levels L_{Aeq} surpassed 100 dBA for most subjects, a three-fold increase to the 4-hour guideline can be expected. Comparatively, earlier work by Tronstad et. al [1] also illustrated high doses, reaching 47 Pa²h. Nevertheless, a pronounced deviation in mean dose should be highlighted between the present study’s account (43.1 Pa²h) and the earlier work (8.9 Pa²h)[1]. This difference in dose suggests the listening environment at the Norwegian events might be less demanding on the ears, and potentially safer according to the WHO dose guideline compared to the events studied here in the Netherlands and Belgium.

This divergence in dose between the Norwegian study and others might be linked to the regulatory difference. With Norway imposing a $L_{Aeq,30min} = 99$ dBA limit, while Belgian and Dutch guidelines are higher at 102dBA and 103dBA, respectively, a disagreement in WHO exceedance can be expected. This guideline difference, along with dose variations, suggest a potentially lower required sound level to comply with the requested WHO guideline of exposure. However, this view should be approached cautiously for several reasons: a 60-minute 100 dBA regulation in Belgium is imposed as well, which aligns with Norway’s limit (Table 1); the 3 dBA difference between guidelines (99dBA vs 102dBA) would only double Pa²h values where a three-fold increase is observed; event variability due to changes in speaker placement and audience area might also be at play; and lastly, the WHO dose guideline has received criticism on its validity for not considering rest periods [1]. In summary, although exposures comply with local guidelines, they signal the need for caution regarding prolonged high sound-level exposures, acknowledging individual subject and event variability.

Event variations illustrated the heavy rainfall notably affected event F3, as indicated by both A- and C-weighted equivalent sound levels (Figure 4). F3 significantly differed from the other events in both L_{Aeq} and L_{Ceq} (Mann Whitney U, $P < 0.01$). Also, significant differences in C-weighted sound levels were observed for F1 and F2 compared to the other events ($P < 0.01$). While the significance was less prominent for F1 and F2 ($P = 4.44e-4$ and $P = 3.36e-3$, respectively) compared to the F3 case ($P = 3.47e-6$), no specific meteorological causes were identified for the former. Hence the F1 and F2 differences are likely attributed to venue or music genre and are not considered separately.

The average A-weighted equivalent sound levels per event generally remained close to the WHO 100 dBA $L_{Aeq,15min}$ guideline, never deviating more than 2.1 dBA, except for F3 (8.2 dBA). Across events, a consistent difference remained between A- and C-weighted sound levels. The incorporation of lower frequencies in the C-weighting underpins this (Figure 4, panel b), which led to averages of C-weighted L_{Ceq} surpassing mean A-weighted levels by at least 8.5 dB for each event (11.4 dB, excluding F3). However, this difference varied among events, implying different sound characteristics potentially due to variations in sound system setup or music genre [35]. The spectral variations were evident in the 62Hz and 125Hz band as well, with differences between both bands fluctuating per event, and the 62Hz band consistently being more pronounced in exposure compared to the 125 Hz band across all events.

5.3 Comparison between personal exposures and FOH regulations & guidelines

To illustrate the exposure properties and its surpassing of local guidelines more effectively, L_{Cpeak} and $L_{Aeq,15min}$ guideline exceedances were considered, although not implying any lack of compliance with local law and regulation. Most out of the 39 subjects exceeded the L_{Cpeak} (135 dBC, 90%) and the $L_{Aeq,15min}$ limits of 100 dBA (WHO, 90%), 102 dBA (BE, 85%) and 103 dBA (NL, 82%). Considering an underlying distribution of both A-weighted and C-weighted sound levels, higher equivalent exposure L_{Aeq} tends to correspond to elevated A- and C-weighted sound levels and their peaks. This correlation might elucidate the higher instances of limit surpassing.

For L_{Cpeak} exceedance (135 dBC), a modest correlation ($r = 0.42$, excluding F3, $P = 13.1e-3$) between the surpass counts and L_{Aeq} is observed. This relation suggests a limited interdependence between C-weighted peak exceedance counts and L_{Aeq} , with L_{Aeq} insufficiently representing peak exposure or its exceedances. Therefore, peak exposure offers an additional dimension of the sound exposure beyond time-weighted values. A distinct and complementary facet of sound exposure at music events is represented by these peaks. The elevated levels in Figure 5 vividly display this discrepancy through considerable fluctuations in exceedance counts corresponding to increased L_{Aeq} . Adding to this, the potential contribution of low frequency sounds to temporal threshold shifts further underlines its complementary value and relevance [36].

In contrast to the limited L_{Cpeak} relation, a stronger and significant correlation was observed between the $L_{Aeq,15min}$ surpassing counts of WHO (100 dBA), BE (102 dBA) and NL (103 dBA) with L_{Aeq} ($P < 0.001$, including and excluding F3). This suggests a better management of the $L_{Aeq,15min}$ through monitoring L_{Aeq} . However, despite this control, a broader spread remains at elevated L_{Aeq} sound levels, underscoring the supplementary insight offered by $L_{Aeq,15min}$ alongside L_{Aeq} .

Still, one should note that the individual sound level exceedances reflect personal exposures and potential risks, not event-specific occurrences or non-compliance with regulation, as the dosimetry solely captured user behavior. Nonetheless, these results contribute a valuable insight into the relationship between imposed guidelines and personal exposure levels, highlighting the variability in individual sound level exposure experiences. User variability in $L_{Aeq,15min}$ levels showed more than three quarters of monitored attendees exceeded all guidelines (WHO, BE, NL) with percentages at 89.7%, 84.6% and 82.1% respectively. This underscores the necessity of detailed time-based exposure assessment alongside the equivalent exposure, L_{Aeq} , to accurately gauge exposure levels.

5.4 Preferred sound level and exposure

Median accumulated 1-minute equivalent sound levels indicated a prevalent individual listening range between 97.5 dBA and 102.5 dBA, lasting around 2.2 hours (median) across subjects. Along with the peaks in exposure duration of $L_{Aeq,15min}$ and L_{Aeq} , (102dBA, or 101dBA), all three measures align closely with the WHO 100 dBA $L_{Aeq,15min}$ guideline and suggest compliance of participant behavior to the guideline. Event-specific sound exposures (Table 6) generally mirrored the 100 dBA guideline, though individual fluctuations were notably large, warranting attention. Front-of-House measurements and limits are thus overall representative of the mean individual exposure.

Additionally, the observed exposure duration peak around 100 dBA contrasts with reported preferred listening levels between 73-85 dBA [37]. These opposing levels do however consider seated concerts and may require a different preferred level. Furthermore, as event sound levels are influenced by multiple factors such as local topography and attendance [2], the desired levels can be compromised for many attendees. Hence, recorded individual sound levels do not necessarily reflect a preferred exposure level and may as well simply reflect level availability. Still, a resemblance between guidelines and exposure levels, peaking around 100 dBA, persist as noted in previous work by Opperman et. al [5]. Also, individual event duration ranged from 4.4 to 11.8 hours, similar to other reported events [1, 2] which extended to 13.5 and 12 hours, respectively.

The consideration of individual exposure preference raises the question of whether stricter guidelines at the Front of House would lead to reduced audience exposure. Lowering sound levels at the FOH would initially limit areas with higher sound levels. However, when a potential 100 dBA preference is considered, the audience might still naturally gather around elevated-level areas although their availability will be reduced. Nonetheless, the consistently found duration peaks around 100 dBA can indicate a possible preference for this sound level among attendees. Further research should verify these trends towards 100 dBA and elucidate the considerable shift from earlier reported comfortable listening levels (73-85 dBA) [37].

5.5 STUDY LIMITATIONS

The uncontrolled outdoor setting of the measurements introduced potential unaccounted individual event variability in the recorded sound levels [2]. Variables as weather conditions (rainfall or heavy wind) and participant positioning relative to the stage were not managed and may have impacted sound recordings. Visitor count and playback system [35] further added expected variation due to restricted access to certain exposure levels. Likewise, peak values L_{Cpeak} should be interpreted cautiously as movement was not accounted for and may have introduced false peaks. Moreover, individual music preference may have also driven behavior variability within a venue, leading to individuals positioning themselves closer to the stage for a desired artist. This personal variability in exposure levels contributes to the observed and desired individual behavior and the general spread of levels for this study, although musical preference was not recorded.

Additionally, small per-event test groups (max 8 participants) operated freely, receiving no specific location instructions. Hence, the results offer only a preliminary glimpse into event and subject variability potential, but nevertheless exhibit notable trends. The assumption of consistent behavior across events may overlook potential differences in behavior per event and associated genre. Similarly, participants' awareness of being monitored could influence their exposure behavior. This influence was minimized by turning the dosimeter information screens off during exposure.

6 CONCLUSION

This study captures individual user levels at large-scale music events to further explore user-specific exposure variability compared to established guidelines. Sound level exposures and doses of 39 participants (42 original) across 6 events were analyzed.

Short-term equivalent sound pressure levels ($L_{Aeq,15min}$) illustrate exposure variability, which is insufficiently captured by equivalent sound exposures (L_{Aeq}) over long exposure windows. Averaging over larger time frames masks variability and individual differences, leading to misguided exposure representations and guideline exceedance despite meeting FOH regulations. In addition, small changes in equivalent exposures can accompany significant shifts in exceedances of WHO guidelines.

High sound exposure levels are prevalent, with 56% of participants exposed to equivalent sound pressure levels (L_{Aeq}) above 100 dBA. Additionally, a significant part of the total duration (36%) was spent above 100 dBA ($L_{Aeq,15min}$), but should be expected as local guidelines specify limits at 102 dBA (BE) and 103 dBA (NL).

Nevertheless, despite most of the exposure time adhering to FOH guidelines at 100 dBA, individual peak differences occurred. Peak occurrences and associated guideline exceedances can be limited as indicated by regression analysis. A reduction of the equivalent sound levels would yield a significant drop in WHO exceedance counts, suggesting a safer listening environment.

Individual guideline exceedances of L_{Cpeak} (135 dBC) and $L_{Aeq,15min}$ provided complementary information on the sound level exposure to L_{Aeq} . Hence, combining long-window measurements (L_{Aeq} and $L_{Aeq,15min}$) with peak measurements L_{Cpeak} allows for a nuanced characterization of exposure that offers insights into average levels, peaks and daily exposure and additional protection against harmful exposure. Nevertheless, a lack of knowledge on the individual participant's locations with respect to the stage does limit insight into where exceeding levels were recorded and could be included in future research.

Lastly, caution for the accumulated exposure dose should be advised, as observed values ranged above two to three times the recommended WHO 4-hour exposure of 16 Pa²h. Reduction of the imposed local guidelines could potentially reduce the excess exposure more closely toward the WHO recommendation while being less demanding on the ear.

7 ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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References

- [1] T.V. Tronstad and F. Gelderblom. Sound exposure during outdoor music festivals. *Noise and Health*, 18:220, Aug. 2016.
- [2] V. Mercier, D. Luy, and B.W. Hohmann. The sound exposure of the audience at a music festival. *Noise Health*, 5(19):51–8, Apr. 2003.
- [3] S. Degeest and E. Clays and P. Corthals and H. Keppler. Lawaaiblootstelling Bij Jongeren : Prevalentie en Risicofactoren van Lawaaigeïnduceerde Gehoorschade en Tinnitus. *LOGOPEDIE (HERENTALS)*, 30(5):25–39, 2017.
- [4] N. Petrescu. Loud music listening. *Mcgill J Med.*, 2(11):169–76, Jul. 2008.
- [5] D.A. Opperman, W. Reifman, R. Schlauch, and S. Levine. Incidence of spontaneous hearing threshold shifts during modern concert performances. *Otolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery*, 134(4):667–673, Apr. 2006.
- [6] A. Yassi and N. Pollock and N. Tran and M. Cheang. Risks to Hearing from a Rock Concert. *Can Fam Physician*, 39:1045–50, May. 1993.
- [7] I. I. Bogoch, R.A. House., and I. Kudla. Perceptions about hearing protection and noise-induced hearing loss of attendees of rock concerts. *Canadian Journal of Public Health*, 96(1):69–72, Jan. 2005.
- [8] L. Carter, W. Williams, D. Black, , and A. Bundy. The leisure-noise dilemma: Hearing loss or hearsay? what does the literature tell us? *Ear Hear*, 35(5):491–505, Sep. 2014.
- [9] F. Zhao, V.K.C. Manchaiah, D. French, and S.M. Price. Music exposure and hearing disorders: An overview. *International Journal of Audiology*, 49(1):54–64, Dec. 2009.

- [10] V. Mercier and B. W. Hohmann. Is Electronically Amplified Music too Loud? What do Young People Think? *Noise Health*, 4(16):47–55, 2002.
- [11] S. Gretchen, S. Flaxman, E. Brunskill, M. Mascarenhas, C.D. Mathers, and M. Finucane. Global and regional hearing impairment prevalence: an analysis of 42 studies in 29 countries. *European Journal of Public Health*, 23(1):146–152, Dec. 2011.
- [12] World Health Organization. Hearing loss due to recreational exposure to loud sounds: a review, 2015.
- [13] Rik Crutzen, Judith Noijen, and Gjalt-Jorn Ygram Peters. Promoting ear plugs at music events: Evaluation of the celebrate safe approach. *International Journal of Audiology*, 60(5):359–364, Oct. 2020.
- [14] J. Eichwald, F. Scinicariello, J.L. Telfer, and Y.I. Carroll. Use of personal hearing protection devices at loud athletic or entertainment events among adults — united states, 2018. *MMWR. Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 67(41):1151–1155, Oct. 2018.
- [15] J. H. Chung, C. M. Des Roches, J. Meunier, and R. D. Eavey. Evaluation of noise-induced hearing loss in young people using a web-based survey technique. *Pediatrics*, 115(4):861–867, Apr. 2005.
- [16] G. G. J. Ramakers, V. J. C. Kraaijenga, G. Cattani, G. A. van Zanten, and W. Grolman. Effectiveness of earplugs in preventing recreational noise-induced hearing loss: A randomized clinical trial. *JAMA Otolaryngology-Head & Neck Surgery*, 142(6):551, Jun. 2016.
- [17] International Organisation for Standardization. Iso 1999:2013 acoustics estimation of noise-induced hearing loss.
- [18] European Commission. Directive 2003/10/ec of the european parliament and of the council of 6 february 2003 on the minimum health and safety requirements regarding exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (noise)., 2003.
- [19] E.F. Beach, J. Mulder, I. O’Brien, and R. Cowan. Overview of laws and regulations aimed at protecting the hearing of patrons within entertainment venues. *European Journal of Public Health*, 31(1):227–233, Oct. 2020.
- [20] World Health Organization. World health organisation global standard for safe listening venues and events, 2022.
- [21] J. Mulder, A. Hill, M. Kok, J. Burton, and M. Lawrence. Towards the global standard for safe listening venues and events. In *in proceedings of the Audio Engineering Society Convention 152*, May. 2022.
- [22] J. Mulder. Amplified music and sound level management; a multi stakeholder perspective. In *in proceedings of the Audio Engineering Society 58th International Conference: Music Induced Hearing Disorders*, Jun. 2015.
- [23] A. Hill, K.List, I. Wiggins, and G. Naylor. A case study on practical live event sound exposure monitoring. In *in proceedings of AES international Conference on Acoustics & Sound Reinforcement*, Jan. 2024.
- [24] VLAREM II. Deel 5. sectorale milieuvoorwaarden voor ingedeelde inrichtingen, hoofdstuk 5.32. ontspanningsinrichtingen en schietstanden, accessed Feb. 27, 2024.
- [25] Rijksoverheid Nederland. Derde convenant preventie gehoorschade versterkte muziek, accessed Feb. 27, 2024.
- [26] N . De Poortere and W. Van Ransbeeck, and S. Keshishzadeh and H. Keppler and I. Dhooge and S. Verhulst. Music festivals : The effect of recreational noise exposure on young adults hearing. In *in proceedings of the ARO (Association for Research in Otolaryngology) 46th Annual Midwinter Conference, Abstracts*, Orlando, Florida, 2023.
- [27] W. V. Ransbeeck, N. D. Poortere, M. Kok, and S. Verhulst. Characteristics of personal sound and noise exposure at music festivals and events. In *in proceedings of the 14th ICBEN conference 152*. ICBEN, May. 2023.
- [28] B. Berglund, T. Lindvall, D. H. Schwela, and WorldHealthOrganization. Guidelines for community noise., 1999.
- [29] Live DMA. Sound regulations in europe, accessed Feb. 27, 2024.
- [30] Legifrance. Code de la santé publique: Section 1: Dispositions générales (articles r1336-1 à r1336-3)., 2017.

- [31] The Norwegian Directorate of Health. Musikkanslegg og helse veileder til arrangører og kommuner, 2011.
- [32] Casella Solutions, accessed Feb. 27, 2024.
- [33] DPA Microphones. The audio consequences of using wind, rain and virus protection on microphones., accessed Feb. 27, 2024.
- [34] J. Mulder, A. Hill, J. Burton, M. Kok, and M. Lawrence. Sound level monitoring at live events, part 2—regulations, practices, and preferences. *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society*, 70(1/2):62–72, Jan. 2022.
- [35] A.J. Hill, J. Mulder, M. Kok, J. Burton, A. Kociper, and A. Berrios. A case study on sound level monitoring and management at large-scale music festivals, 2019.
- [36] B Kylin. Temporary threshold shift and auditory trauma following exposure to steady-state noise. an experimental and field study. *Acta Otolaryngol Suppl*, 152:1–93, 1960.
- [37] A. Tereping. Listener preference for concert sound levels: Do louder performances sound better? *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society*, 64:138–146, Mar. 2016.